

Journal Policy Toolkit

Every journal requires policies for [transparent processes](#). Certain policies are also required for ensuring your journal is indexed and discoverable. This document contains a list of example policy types, alongside descriptions and example language. When these policies are required is also noted.

Need help drafting a policy or have questions? Email [\[contact\]](#) to meet with one of our staff.

Author Publication Agreement

An important document for every journal to have. This will outline the responsibilities of the author and the journal. This can include information on if there is a copyright transfer, or if the author retains copyright. We encourage journals to use our [\[internal link: publication agreement template\]](#) as a starting point.

Read more about copyright and OJS in our [\[internal link: copyright and licensing considerations document\]](#).

Copyright Policy / Copyright Notice / Copyright Statement

DOAJ, OJS field

A Journal's copyright notice informs readers of copyright status (who holds copyright of the article) and which Creative Commons license was assigned to the article. The copyright notice appears on the journal submission page and authors are asked to check a box as part of the submission process that says "Yes, I agree to abide by the terms of the copyright statement." The copyright policy should be easily discoverable by potential authors and reviewers.

For more background on copyright and licensings visit our [\[internal link: copyright and licensing considerations document\]](#).

We suggest a default policy described in the sample Copyright Notices / Statements provided below, organized by suggested CC licence.

CC BY

All authors published in [\[Journal Title\]](#) retain copyright and grant the journal right of first publication with the work simultaneously licensed under an [International Creative Commons Attribution License \(CC BY 4.0\)](#), which means that anyone may share, copy, and adapt the material for any purpose, as long as they credit the author and this journal.

Journal Policy Toolkit

CC BY-ND

All authors published in [Journal Title] retain copyright and grant the journal right of first publication with the work simultaneously licensed under an [International Creative Commons Attribution-NoDerivatives License \(CC BY-ND 4.0\)](#), which means that anyone may share, copy, and adapt the material for any purpose, as long as they credit the author and this journal and do not distribute the modified version.

CC BY-NC

All authors published in [Journal Title] retain copyright and grant the journal right of first publication with the work simultaneously licensed under an [International Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial License \(CC-BY-NC 4.0\)](#), which means that anyone may share, copy, and adapt the material for non-commercial purposes, as long as they credit the author and this journal.

CC BY-NC-ND

All authors published in [Journal Title] retain copyright and grant the journal right of first publication with the work simultaneously licensed under an [International Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives License \(CC BY-NC-ND 4.0\)](#), which means that anyone may share, copy, and adapt the material for non-commercial purposes, as long as they credit the author and this journal and do not distribute the modified version.

Digital archiving policy

DOAJ and OJS suggested section

Suggested default policy

This journal is archived with the [Public Knowledge Project \(PKP\) Preservation Network](#) and [Scholars Portal Journals](#). These programs offer a decentralized and distributed preservation, perpetual access, and preservation of the authentic original version of the content.

Deposit Policy or Self-Archiving

Provides information on authors self-archiving rights.

A statement clarifying to authors what their rights are for self-archiving, covering their rights to self-archive preprint, accepted, final publisher versions of the article, usually in places like

Journal Policy Toolkit

their own website or institutional repository. The DOAJ requires a policy to be listed for a journal and checks what policy is listed for the journal on services like SHERPA/RoMEO <http://www.sherpa.ac.uk/romeo/index.php>.

Suggested default policy (if authors transfer copyright to journal)

Under the terms of the Creative Commons license, authors are permitted to post their work online in institutional/disciplinary repositories or on their own websites. Pre-print versions posted online should include a citation and link to the final published version in [Journal Title] as soon as the issue is available; post-print versions (including the final publisher's PDF) should include a citation and link to the journal's website.

Suggested default policy (if authors retain rights)

Authors are encouraged to deposit the published version in an institutional / disciplinary repository immediately on publication. Pre-print versions posted online should include a citation and link to the final published version in [Journal Title] as soon as the issue is available; post-print versions (including the final publisher's PDF) should include a citation and link to the journal's website.

[Example Deposit Policy](#) under the fourth bullet of the Copyright and Licenses section

Open access statement or policy

DOAJ required

This is a statement which clearly outlines to the reader the journal's policy about the access requirements of the journal. This policy should explicitly note that your journal does not charge an article processing charge (APC) to make content open access. There may be some overlap between the open-access statement and the copyright policy. It is possible for these to be combined into one larger statement.

Suggested default Open Access Statement

[Journal Title] is a diamond open access journal that provides immediate open access to its content on the principle that making research freely available to the public supports the greater global exchange of knowledge.

Authors will never be charged to submit or publish a manuscript through [Journal Title], and all articles will be made available under a [Creative Commons license](#), as indicated in the Copyright Notice section under the [\[Submissions page\]](#).

Journal Policy Toolkit

Privacy Statement

Informs how the journal will handle users who registers data. There is a default language that we provide and a detailed template below.

[internal link: Suggested default privacy statement]

Post-Publication Corrections and Retractions Statement

The following are items to consider when drafting your journal's policy on post-publication corrections and retractions:

A post-publication correction is an edit to the content or metadata of an article that has already been published. These include small changes (e.g. correcting a citation) and larger alterations (e.g. editing data). When errors significantly impact an article, a retraction can be issued to indicate that the article is no longer a reliable research source.

It's best to have a policy on post-publication corrections and retractions established before an issue arises, so your journal can deal with inquiries in a timely and effective manner.

Impacts of Post-Dissemination Corrections

Directly editing an article after publication can result in improper citations, improper indexation and additional delays. Metadata and small typographical errors may be corrected by editing the original document. Otherwise, avoid direct edits by using errata and retractions.

Errata and Retractions

When the error is noticeable but does not impact the main argument(s) of an article, publish an erratum. The erratum should clearly state the error, where it appears, and how it has been corrected. Errata may be published in the journal's next issue, or may be added to the current issue through versioning (which retains the original article). Regardless of where it is published, the erratum should be linked on the page of the original article.

When the article is no longer reliable or ethical due to an error, a retraction is required. The retraction must explicitly state that the article has been retracted and detail the reason(s) for retraction. A retraction notice should appear in every format of the retracted article, as well as the original article page.

Examples

The following are examples of post-publication corrections statements:

- [Critical Gambling Studies: About the Journal](#)
- [Canadian Journal of Emergency Nursing: About the Journal](#)

Journal Policy Toolkit

Sources

This policy is based on the following sources:

- [COPE: Dealing with Concerns about the Integrity of Published Research](#)
 - [COPE: Post-Publication Critiques](#)
 - [COPE: Retraction Guidelines](#)
 - [Érudit: Policy on Post-Dissemination Corrections](#)
 - [PKP: Corrections and Retractions - Journal Policies and Workflows](#)
-

Publications Ethics and malpractice statements

Required for Scopus indexing

For this statement it is important to show that you have thought through the responsibility of the author, publisher and reviewers. This statement will also require you to consider any financial or intellectual relationships that may be considered a conflict of interest. A good resource for guidelines include [COPE \(Committee on Publication Ethics\)](#).

[Example Conflict of Interest Statement 1](#) (for authors)

[Example Conflict of Interest Statement 2](#) (bottom of “about” page”)

[Example Publication Ethics Statement 1](#)

[Example of Ethics Statement 2](#)

[Example of Ethics Statement 3](#)

General Ethical publishing guidelines from Weave

<https://journals.publishing.umich.edu/weaveux/site/guidelines/>

Research Misconduct Policy (Plagiarism, Incorrect Citation, Falsified Data, etc.)

This statement should describe your process for identification of and dealing with allegations of research misconduct.

Example language from the [Indiana University Bloomington New Journal Toolkit](#):

The editors of [Journal Title] will take reasonable steps to identify and prevent the publication of papers where research misconduct has occurred, including plagiarism, citation manipulation, and data falsification/fabrication, among others. In the event that the editors are made aware of any allegation of research misconduct relating to a published article in their journal, the editor shall follow the [Committee on Publication Ethics guidelines](#) in dealing with allegations.

Journal Policy Toolkit

Scope Statement

Required for applications to most indexing services

Consider what the journal hopes to accomplish and how that will happen. Consider including what type of submissions and formats are accepted, and outlining the criteria of who can submit to the journal.

[Example Scope Statement](#)

Sponsorship Disclosure

There is a field in OJS to note this for transparency as applicable.

[Example Sponsorship Disclosure statement](#)

Resources

<http://pkp.sfu.ca/ojs/docs/userguide/2.3.1/journalManagementPages.html>
<https://blog.doaj.org/category/open-access-policy/>
<https://jps.library.utoronto.ca/index.php/pubguide/copyright>

Example Journal Policies

- <https://journal.lib.uoguelph.ca/index.php/perj/about>
- <https://spectrumjournal.ca/index.php/spectrum/about/submissions>
- <https://journals.library.ualberta.ca/eblip/index.php/EBLIP/about>
- <https://jisc-pub.org/about/>